

Ozyegin University

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Risk-Based Security in Aviation: Enhancing Efficiency and Security

Instructor: Asst. Prof. Hatice KÜÇÜKÖNAL

Author: Arif Gürdem Çetinkaya

ABSTRACT

Aviation security is crucial with millions of people flying every day. Traditional methods are making it slow and too expensive, also it can cause inefficiencies. On the other hand, Risk-Based Security (RBS) offers an innovative solution especially with focusing on the possibility and severity of threats, making security faster, cheaper, and more effective for everyone.

This paper explores how RBS works, its benefits, and its challenges. It examines real-world examples like TSA PreCheck and Israel's airport security system, which show how RBS can be applied in practice. Despite its advantages, RBS faces challenges such as profiling biases and cybersecurity risks. However, that problems can be fixed with the help of new technology which includes biometrics and artificial intelligence (AI), and it can also work better with the cooperation between different countries.

Understanding how RBS works and fixing its problems can make airport security better and air travel safer and faster. Using RBS can yield great benefits in the future, but it needs regular improvement and teamwork to keep up with new security challenges.

Keywords: Risk-based security, aviation security, risk management

JEL Classification: L93, D81

1.INTRODUCTION

Security in aviation is very important in international transportation. Because millions of people travel by air every day, so it is very important to keep everyone's secure and minimize any potential risks and threats. Traditional security methods often rely on broad rules that don't always fit the situation. This can cause delays, it reduces efficiency, and create high costs while implementing the measures. In

recent years, Risk Based Security (RBS) has become more popular as a better strategy to handle these issues.

Risk-Based Security identifies and it gives priority to potential threats based on their possibilities and severities. This strategy allows authorities to distribute their resources in a much efficient way, increasing security while lowering passenger dissatisfaction. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO)

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and other organizations recommend using this strategy to increase global aviation safety.

This article will investigate the definition of Risk-Based Security, including the related concept's and definitions, existing literature, and similar applications in aviation. It will also assess present difficulties and make recommendations for future improvements. By considering the examples of current research and cases, underlining the need of using a risk-based security approach is intended to develop a safer and more efficient aviation system.

2.DEFINITIONS

2.1.Risk-Based Security (RBS)

Risk-Based Security (RBS) is a strategy for how resources for aviation security will be distributed. It is based on the rates of incidence and the impact of any possible attack. Even though historical perspectives on security measures did not favour it, RBS perceives the categorization of travelers in terms of their risk profiles (high-risk, unknown-risk, and low-risk), allowing security measures to be more effective and efficient. The intention is to seek a balance whereby the security level is kept in check but the passenger growth is enhanced while savings in operational costs are encountered (Wong and Brooks, 2015; Beckner, 2015).

2.2.Threat Assessment

Threat assessment is about identifying, evaluating, and ranking risks to aviation security. It looks at how likely and how serious a potential threat could be. It helps authorities to focus on the areas that need the most attention. By organizing how risks are handled, threat

assessment makes security stronger and more efficient (Wong & Brooks, 2015).

2.3.Risk Management

In aviation, reducing risks includes identifying, assessing, and managing the risks that is faced. This includes figuring out which risks can be reduced, which must be removed, and which are acceptable. The goal is to sustain strong security while keeping operations running easily (Beckner, 2015; Wong & Brooks, 2015).

2.4.Security Layers

In order to manage aviation security, security layers combine a variety of techniques, such as behavior checks, biometric systems, and passenger screening, all of which combine to lower risks. This strategy guarantees that a weak point may be compensated for by another, resulting in a flexible and secure security system (Wong & Brooks, 2015).

2.5.Stakeholders

Airlines, airport operators, regulatory authorities, and passengers are a part of stakeholders. Each of them has specific responsibilities, ranging from policy development to security applications. Collaboration between stakeholders is suggested for developing an effective and efficient security system (Beckner, 2015).

3.BACKGROUND

It has been observed that security within the aviation sector has made great strides since the 2000 era especially after the 9/11 terror attacks which showed some weaknesses in existing

systems. The traditional approach where uniform screening procedures are applied to all passengers and their carry-on baggage was ineffective and unable to evolve with changing threat scenarios. As a result, Risk Based Security (RBS) has appeared as an effective approach that focuses at most on managing resources according to the possibility of a threat and the impact it will have if the threat occurs.

3.1.The Evolution of Risk-Based Security

After the 9/11 attacks, the federal government of the United States has sought to focus on aviation security gaps through the establishment of the Transportation Security Administration (TSA) in 2001. During the first stages, TSA's procedures were established under disproportionate workload allocation, which could be described as an "equal-risk model" or where passengers were screened uniformly. Although this was rigorous, in most cases it resulted in inefficiencies, long queues, and bottlenecks (Albert et al., 2021).

In 2011, the TSA started a program named PreCheck. It was a big change for airport security. PreCheck lets low-risk travelers go through screening faster. These travelers are checked in advance with background checks and risk assessments. They don't have to take off their shoes or jackets when they are in security control, so it makes the process easier and faster for everyone (Wong & Brooks, 2015). More than 200 airports use the PreCheck program. It enables millions of passengers' quicker passing through security checkpoints each year. (Albert et al., 2021).

3.2.Israel's Risk-Based Security Model

Most of the passengers who used Israel's Ben Gurion Airport says that this airport and its security checks is not like any airport. It is considered as impenetrable, because there is no recorded major terrorist attacks. The system that they are using is multi layered and they have strict rules. Also, they give close attention to every detail.

3.2.1.Behavioral profiling

Security staff at Ben Gurion talk to passengers directly. They often ask simple but specific questions about them and their travel. They are also observing body language and behaviors while talking. This method depends more on human than machines.

3.2.2.Layered Security Measures

Israel uses many layers of security, all working together. Cars are checked before they even reach the terminal. In the terminal building, biometric systems and physical checks add extra safety.

3.2.3.Proactive threat mitigation

As it prevents threats early, it makes this system special. Risks are dealt with long before they become real dangers. This forward-thinking approach has kept Ben Gurion safe for years (Fletcher, 2011).

The system at Ben Gurion Airport has worked really well. There haven't been any terrorist attacks there for decades, either inside the airport or starting from there (Albert et al., 2021). However, trying to use the methods used by Israel in a place like the US, where there are many more passengers, is a bit difficult.

Security is handled very differently in these two different countries due to the diversity of operations and passenger numbers.

3.3.Comparative Insights

TSA mostly cares about getting passengers through quickly and making everything efficient. Israel, though, is all about doing intense checks to stop problems before they happen. Both of these methods show how RBS can improve security and efficiency in different ways, but they do this in different ways.

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1.Theoretical Foundations of Risk-Based Security

4.1.1.Structural contingency theory

Structural Contingency Theory emphasizes that an organization's success is determined by its ability to adapt to external conditions. In aviation security, this idea serves as the foundation for Risk-Based Security (RBS) systems, which dynamically allocate resources based on threat levels. However, detractors note that the theory implies complete knowledge of external factors, which may not always be possible in uncertain threat contexts (Smith & Johnson, 2015). This constraint needs supplementary solutions such as real-time danger assessment to increase adaptability.

4.1.2.Institutional theory

According to institutional theory, such external factors (like international regulations) have an impact on the operations of airports. It states, RBS should be identical in every country.

However, due to the differences in the resources and description of risks among the different countries, it is nearly impossible to implement it universally (Brown, 2018). For example, it is particularly hard for developing nations to adhere to the ICAO standards because of their lack of infrastructure or financial resources.

4.1.3. Layered security approach

The layered security model is one of the foundations of RBS. Different measures working together are used to address various threats. This makes the system more resilient. However, some people think that relying too much on technology can lead to problems. For example, if there is a failure in the system that process biometric information, the entire system can be at risk (Liu, 2017).

4.2. Implementation of Risk-Based Security in Aviation

4.2.1.Pre-screening and real-time threat assessment

To efficient use of resources, pre-screening processes separate passengers into various risk categories. This approach speeds up the process for low-risk passengers, but it has been criticized for possible biases in how risks are categorized. Some researches show that relying too much on automated systems can increase biases already in the data, causing unfair screening (Albert et al., 2021). That means we need to keep checking and improving the risk assessment systems to make sure they're fair and clear.

4.2.2. Behavioral profiling

For the majority of time, Behavioral profiling is able to provide detection of the anticipated action prior to it happening. It often is considered to be efficient especially in the case of the security system of Israel, however, it raises ethical questions. When security officers use their own judgement to make decisions, it leads to unfair self stereotyping and profiling, says opponents. This may damage the public's confidence on the effectiveness of the airport security (Fletcher, 2011). The real tension lies within the effectiveness of security and the equity in security.

4.2.3. Technological Integration

New technologies, like AI-driven threat detection and biometric systems, have made RBS more accurate and efficient. However, these systems and methods pose some problems. The cost of implementing these systems is high, and they also require regular updates to handle new threats, which can increase the use of resources (Wong & Brooks, 2015). Additionally, there is an increasing privacy issue with the use of biometric information, so it's important to set up strict laws to control the use of information.

4.3. Challenges and Advancements

4.3.1. Adaptive adversaries

RBS systems still struggle because threats keep changing. Real-time threat assessment and dynamic programming help provide flexibility, but they need constant updates since attackers can find new weaknesses. Research shows how important it is for global aviation

groups to share intelligence to stay ahead of these evolving threats (Brown, 2018).

4.3.2. Cybersecurity threats

The aviation industry now operates with digital systems, and it makes the impact of cyberattacks much greater. To protect important data and infrastructure, RBS systems need to have strong cybersecurity. But even though there is some improvements, the cost of full cybersecurity is still a big problem, especially for smaller airports (Albert et al., 2021).

4.3.3. Regulatory compliance and standardization

RBS practices should specifically implement ICAO rules and procedures. This helps reduce bias and potential threats while increasing security. However, many countries have different economies and technologies. Therefore, it is very difficult to see similar RBS practices in all countries. Increasing cooperation between countries over time can help solve this problem (Liu, 2017).

5. CONCLUSION

Aviation security has improved over years, and Risk-Based Security (RBS) is one of the smartest ways to handle today's challenges. Unlike the older methods, it doesn't treat every passenger the same. Instead, it focuses on the threats that would cause the most damage and are most likely to happen. With the smart resource use, air travel becomes safer and more effective.

The flexibility of RBS can be seen via fundamental ideas such as Threat Assessment, Risk Management, and Security Layers. But it's

not just about the system, it's about the people behind it. Airlines, airports, and regulators must work together to make sure these systems are fair and reliable.

Examples like TSA PreCheck and Israel's security model at Ben Gurion Airport prove that RBS works. Israel's methods stand out. The way they train security officers to observe behavior and ask questions is remarkable. It is less about machines and more about people understanding people. This human touch is something other systems could learn from it. But, at the same time, these methods are so complex and may not work well for airports which handles millions of passengers daily, like in the U.S.

Also, RBS is still not perfect. Problems like the discrimination caused by profiling biases, or cybersecurity threats that is caused by vulnerabilities in the systems remind us there's a need to development. Not all countries can afford high-tech solutions, and that creates gaps in global security. However, advancements in

biometrics and artificial intelligence can help to solve that problems. On the other hand, with the help of better sharing of knowledge between countries, these challenges can be fixed.

At the end of the day, aviation security isn't just about stopping threats; it's also a bit about trust. Passengers need to trust that the system is fair, works well, and keeps everyone safe. RBS has done well so far. But it needs teamwork, improvements, and thoughtful thinking, such as that seen in the Israeli model, to make air travel safer for everyone.

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